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EOSC EDEN Data Management Plan

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Deliverable Abstract

The EOSC EDEN Data Management Plan outlines the plan of action for the collection, generation, processing, and preservation of data of EOSC EDEN to ensure the project complies with rights and responsibilities related to data management as stated in the Grant Agreement. This Data Management Plan is a living document that will be updated throughout the project lifecycle. The initial version was prepared under Work Package 5 in 2025 as deliverable D5.2. The current edition represents the 18-month iteration. The implementation of this document is the responsibility of all EOSC EDEN project partners.

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			Roxanne Wyns
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			Andrea Davidson
V2.0	30/06/2026	Updated version	Anu Märkälä

TERMINOLOGY

Terminology/Acronym	Definition
bwf	Broadcast Wave Format
CC-BY	Creative Commons Attribution
CERN	European Council for Nuclear Research
CODATA	Committee on Data of the International Science Council
CSC	IT Center for Science Ltd.
csv	comma-separated values
DC	Dublin Core
DDI	Data Documentation Initiative Alliance
DMP	Data Management Plan
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
DPC	Digital Preservation Coalition

DSSC	Data Spaces Support Centre
EAB	External Advisory Board
EC	European Commission
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ERIC	European Research Infrastructure Consortium
ESFRI	European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures
FAIR	Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reuse
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GLAM	Galleries, Libraries, Archives, Museums
HTTP	Hypertext Transfer Protocol
INFRAEOSC	Enabling an operational, open, and FAIR EOSC ecosystem
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
KU Leuven	Katholieke Universiteit Leuven
LTDP	Long-Term Data Preservation
NDA	Non-disclosure agreement
OAI-PMH	Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting
OPF	Open Preservation Foundation
ORCID	Open Researcher and Contributor ID
ORE	Open Research Europe
OS	Open Science
pdf/a	Portable Document Format Archive
PID	Persistent Identifiers
PMB	Project management board
PMO	Project management office
RDA	Research Data Alliance
RIs	Research Infrastructures
tsv	Tab-separated values
UESSEX-UKDA	University of Essex
UiT	The University of Tromsø – The Arctic University of Norway
UNESCO	United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization
W3C	World Wide Web Consortium
WebVTT	Web Video Text Tracks Format
WP	Work Package
XML	Extensible Markup Language

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Executive Summary

EOSC EDEN - “Enhancing Digital preservation strategies at European and National level” - is funded by the European Union under the Horizon Europe programme and aims to support and facilitate the practices and standards of long-term data preservation. EOSC EDEN is dedicated to the INFRAEOSC destination work programme “Enabling an operational, open and FAIR EOSC ecosystem.” EOSC EDEN aims to develop a framework for evaluating data for long-term preservation and a model for re-appraisal, as well as identify practices that support long-term preservation strategies in Europe. The project will develop a set of user-centred tools, services, and standards to support the establishment of a European distributed infrastructure for long-term preservation, curation, and access. This Data Management Plan outlines EOSC EDEN's action plan for handling data that is created during and after the project to ensure that the project complies with rights and responsibilities related to data management as stated in the Grant Agreement; these actions involve data collection, documentation, ethical issues, storage and backup, preservation and sharing. This document follows guidelines on FAIR data management to ensure that the data generated through the project's actions are managed responsibly. EOSC EDEN will be implemented following Open Science principles and will make sure data is protected following the General Data Protection Regulation. This Data Management Plan is a living document that will be updated throughout the project lifecycle. The initial version is prepared under Work Package 5 as deliverable D5.2. This edition reflects the first 18-month iteration and includes several minor updates, such as a link to the EOSC EDEN GitHub and the preservation of survey and interview data. The implementation of this document is the responsibility of all EOSC EDEN project partners.

1 Data Summary

The EOSC EDEN¹ Data Management Plan (DMP) outlines the plan of action for the collection, generation, processing, preservation, and sharing of data by the EOSC EDEN consortium members by following the rights and responsibilities established in the Grant Agreement. This document follows the FAIR principles² to ensure that data generated through actions are managed responsibly. EOSC EDEN will be implemented in accordance with Open Science³ and ensure data is protected following the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)⁴. EOSC EDEN is relevant to the INFRAEOSC⁵ destination work programme “Enabling an operational, open and FAIR EOSC ecosystem.” EOSC EDEN will process the data in line with the principle of “as open as possible and as closed as necessary.” This DMP serves as a living document that has been updated at month 18 and will be updated again at month 36 of the project. Project partners are responsible for the collection, transfer, and storage of data from their own activities within the project into the shared working space set up by the PMO.

1.1 Data types and formats

Data will be generated during the implementation of the EOSC EDEN project through different engagement activities such as surveys, interviews, and workshops for the collection of stakeholder needs, which will translate into specifications for the development of the framework and the re-appraisal model, the technical specifications, etc. There will also be internal project consortium meetings, collective consortium meetings, and other outreach activities throughout the project’s lifetime. Data will also accompany the development of the services and testing in use cases and discipline-specific pilots. Within EOSC EDEN, the following categories of data to be managed are foreseen:

A. Quantitative and qualitative data collected through surveys, expert interviews, workshops, and bootcamps.

Qualitative data containing personally identifiable information, such as name, organisation, and role within the organisation, should be collected and retained to enable contact with expert and specialist networks, EOSC project representatives, etc., throughout the lifetime of the project.

Personally identifiable data needs to be collected with the informed consent of the stakeholder participant and shared according to the agreed purpose: 1) within the restricted context of the project, access rights are managed by the party responsible for overall engagement (WP4, led by KU Leuven), 2) across WPs for direct engagement with stakeholder participants who are open to a broader engagement with the project, 3) publicly for those stakeholder participants consenting to have their name and affiliation published on the website, as part of reports, etc. for their own visibility (e.g. training and participation awards). In the case of 1) and 2), all data will be anonymised unless otherwise consented to by the participants and shared in an aggregated manner when included in public reports and deliverables, as well as with the sister project FIDELIS⁶. Where relevant, these data will be published with open access as a dataset in the EOSC EDEN

¹ EOSC EDEN. <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101188015>

² The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. <https://www.nature.com/articles/sdata201618>

³ Open Science.

https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/strategy/strategy-research-and-innovation/our-digital-future/open-science_en

⁴ GDPR. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32016R0679>

⁵ INFRAEOSC.

https://rea.ec.europa.eu/funding-and-grants/horizon-europe-research-infrastructure/enabling-operational-open-and-fair-eosc-ecosystem-infraeosc_en

⁶ FIDELIS. <https://eosc.eu/eu-project/fidelis/>

Zenodo community⁷ and linked to the report or deliverable as underlying data. In the case of 3), the data will be archived in the EOSC EDEN project database Eduuni-Wiki with appropriate data safeguards.

B. Data based on revisiting previous studies and existing frameworks, guidelines, and practices and new data generated by the project.

This data will be included in the reports and deliverables of the project. Where relevant, these data will be published with open access as a dataset in the EOSC EDEN Zenodo community and linked to the report or deliverable as underlying data.

C. All public presentations, reports, deliverables, and other outputs will be published with quality metadata and license information in the Zenodo community.

The results of the project and underlying data (without identifiable information) will be archived and kept in accordance with the common practice of a minimum retention period of 10 years.

D. Software code will be managed in Git repositories and released as open source.

The software code generated from the project will be managed and publicly shared in Git repositories via the EOSC EDEN GitHub⁸ organization.

The estimated volume of data to be archived and published is around 1 TB. The file formats used for data publication must be widely recognised and follow established good practices for long-term preservation in trustworthy repositories, ensuring compatibility with the sustainability and accessibility standards of the chosen repository. Table 1 lists the foreseen data or output generated by EOSC EDEN.

Table 1 List of data or output to be generated by EOSC EDEN

Content	Format	Preservation	Sensitive Information	Dissemination Level
Surveys & Interviews	html, tsv/csv, ods/ xlsx, pdf, mp4, wav, bwf, srt/web VTT	Raw interview and survey data will be stored at the partner's institution securely, and the transcription of the interview can be shared via CSC's SD Connect ⁹ , with certain sensitive data allowed. The anonymised data and results will be downloadable and shareable with data processors within the EOSC EDEN project. The results will be published on Zenodo in an anonymous form as part of the deliverables or as underlying data to enable wider access and dissemination.	Available to data processors only. Written informed consent will be requested prior to the survey or interviews. If any personal information is inadvertently included, it will be anonymised before publication to ensure privacy and confidentiality.	Anonymised results will be made public.

⁷ EOSC EDEN Zenodo community.

<https://zenodo.org/communities/eosceden/records?q=&|list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest>

⁸ EOSC EDEN GitHub. <https://github.com/EOSC-EDEN>

⁹ SD Connect. <https://sd-connect.csc.fi/>

Content	Format	Preservation	Sensitive Information	Dissemination Level
Project deliverables, reports, and specifications	pdf	The deliverables and milestones will be submitted to the European Commission via the Funding & Tenders Portal by the PMO. If a deliverable is published with the disclaimer text, the disclaimer will be deleted when the Commission has officially approved the deliverable. All public deliverables will be uploaded to Zenodo and the project website.	Author information (name, affiliation, etc.)	Final deliverable reports will be publicly shared in the EOSC EDEN Zenodo community and through the EOSC EDEN website.
Scientific publications		All scientific publications deriving from the project will be diamond open access, accompanied by a DOI and reported in the EC Funding & Tenders portal as per the Grant Agreement.	Author information (name, affiliation, etc.)	Scientific publications will be in diamond open access publishing venues, e.g., Open Research Europe or other venues complying with EC requirements and recommendations.
Recordings or materials of webinars and workshops	mp4, pdf, csv, srt/Web VTT	The recordings will be published on YouTube and Zenodo, or platforms/archives of consortium partners (if applicable). Other materials (e.g., PowerPoint Presentation slides) will be published as pdf on Zenodo	Participant information, incl. chat, will be removed from the recordings. If necessary, participants will be asked to give additional consent for the publication of recordings, incl. their contributions to the session, in the registration form.	Recordings will be publicly available on YouTube, the EOSC EDEN website, and Zenodo upon speakers' and participants' (where applicable) consent.

Funding must be clearly stated in all public documents and files in line with Horizon Europe funding requirements. Instructions on acknowledging EU funding have been added to the EOSC EDEN Wiki by the PMO, with access restricted to partners only¹⁰. The EOSC EDEN consortium acknowledges the importance of Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) and is committed to their transparent and appropriate management.

To promote openness and collaboration, the software produced by the project will be licensed under an open-source licence as recommended by the Free Software Foundation¹¹. A suitable licence is agreed later, as it may depend, e.g., on the third-party software libraries that the produced software uses. Software codes will be published through the EOSC EDEN GitHub organization.

¹⁰ EOSC EDEN acknowledgement instruction. <https://Wiki.eduuni.fi/x/aIN9IQ>.

¹¹ Free Software Licensing Resources. https://www.fsf.org/licensing/education/?set_language=da

All public presentations, reports, deliverables, and other outputs will be published with quality metadata and license information in the Zenodo community to be established for the project. This will automatically generate a Digital Object Identifier (DOI) with DataCite and DC-compliant machine-actionable metadata. The default license for these public documents will be a Creative Commons license suitable for data sharing (CC-BY License), but changes might apply depending on external contributions. Other materials that cannot be shared with a wider audience due to legal restrictions or ethical concerns will be kept in the restrictive working environment of the project with proper access control mechanisms in place or anonymised.

1.2 Data re-use

EOSC EDEN plans to reuse data from previous studies and existing frameworks, guidelines, and practices. EOSC EDEN will leverage several existing initiatives and previous investments and preferably re-use services developed or in development by third parties - including EU-funded projects. To develop and establish a framework to identify what data are candidates for long-term preservation, EOSC EDEN will extend existing practices around FAIRness and technical quality of data with re-use fitness metrics covering digital preservation principles such as file format sustainability criteria, significant properties, file format validity and metadata completeness. A re-appraisal process will be introduced into the data lifecycle and, in addition to regular ingest, the re-use fitness model will be applied to re-appraisal.

The Data and Process Framework for long-term digital preservation (LTDP) to be established in EOSC EDEN will build on previous efforts and input obtained through comprehensive community engagement within and across disciplines and data-type-oriented settings.

Some relevant stakeholder groups and communities already exist. EOSC EDEN will mobilise trustworthy repositories, archives, and other providers of services for long-term preservation to contribute to and complement the network of trustworthy digital repositories built by the FIDELIS project. Reusing data from ongoing and initiated EOSC-related projects and initiatives is in the plan, such as data from the EOSC Association, Skills4EOSC, FIDELIS, OSTrails, FAIRCORE4EOSC, FAIR-IMPACT, and EVERSE. EOSC EDEN participates in ongoing projects to embed, reuse, and extend curation and preservation services generated through previous or ongoing efforts (e.g., planned boot camps).

1.3 Data utility

Collectively, the data and outputs of EOSC EDEN will help stakeholders responsible for data production, stewardship, and long-term distribution and preservation achieve the ultimate goals of quality management in a long-term perspective: (i) provide valuable information to understand the data, (ii) ensure the data are reliable and ready to be used according to non-functional requirements, and (iii) ensure the data meet functional requirements (when the purpose is known) or providing the information necessary to make self-assessments of fitness-for-purpose of the data (when the purpose is unknown). The data collected through activities and events in EOSC EDEN are intended to be beneficial to the following stakeholders:

- Digital archives, repositories, and registries (global, European, national, institutional, thematic/specialist)
- Digital object curators and preservationists/archivists - composed of diverse organisational representations and digital specialisation (data types, files, Linked Data, semantic artefacts, software, and code)
- EOSC related projects (ongoing and starting, e.g. Skills4EOSC, FIDELIS, OSTrails, FAIRCORE4EOSC, FAIR-IMPACT, EVERSE)
- EOSC Partnership (EOSC-A, EC)
- DSSC, Data Spaces
- National networks with a focus on research data management or digital long-term preservation

- GLAM sector (Galleries, Libraries, Archives, Museums)
- International OS, standards, and preservation-related initiatives (e.g. RDA, OPF, DPC, GO FAIR, W3C Data on the Web Best Practices group, DDI Cross-Domain Integration Framework)
- ERIC Forum, ESFRI, RIs, research communities, domain-specific networks, domain-specific repositories, Science Clusters, OSCARS project.
- National funders and policymakers
- Data stewards and researchers.

2 FAIR Data

Open Science and a commitment to FAIR data and long-term preservation of the data are key to how activities within EOSC EDEN will be implemented. The EOSC EDEN project supports the implementation of FAIR-enabled practices at European, national, and institutional levels. Data generated and collected through EOSC EDEN will be open access and FAIR, i.e., findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable, unless there are valid reasons to opt-out, which will be given in the DMP, e.g., due to privacy/data protection considerations. Data collectors/creators need to ensure that data provenance (e.g., who created the data, modification history) is adequately documented throughout the data lifecycle, where necessary. In addition, the CARE¹² and TRUST¹³ principles are supported and considered as well, where applicable.

2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Data generated and collected by EOSC EDEN will be deposited in open online data repositories, making the data findable. Zenodo will be the recommended repository for EOSC EDEN data and project output, including deliverables, specifications, and milestone reports. An “EOSC EDEN Community” is established in Zenodo and its records are automatically searchable in the EU Open Research Repository on that platform.¹⁴ Zenodo will automatically register a DOI, a globally unique persistent identifier, for a record once published. The EOSC EDEN Zenodo repository catalogues data and metadata with the following minimum required elements: title, author(s), ORCID, keywords, publication date, description, access right, license and funding (European Commission with value 101188015). Rich metadata is recommended throughout the WPs. In Zenodo, metadata is stored internally in JSON format according to a defined JSON schema, and it can be exported in several standard formats such as MARCXML¹⁵, Dublin Core¹⁶, and DataCite Metadata Schema¹⁷ (according to the OpenAIRE Guidelines). EOSC EDEN outputs will include the keywords ‘EOSC’, ‘EOSC EDEN’, and ‘Long-Term Preservation.’ Metadata of published data will be made open under a Creative Common Public Domain Dedication (CC 0) or equivalent. Zenodo metadata is harvested by several aggregators, such as DataCite Commons, OpenAIRE, and the EOSC EU Node Resource Hub.

For project management, EOSC EDEN uses Eduuni Wiki¹⁸ as the main collaboration working platform, and Google Drive is used as an “add-on” for collaborative writing of technical reports, deliverables, milestones, presentations, etc. The EOSC EDEN Wiki space is meant for information sharing and note-taking across the project consortium. All project members who have been admitted access by the project PMO can view and edit the content in the EOSC EDEN Wiki space. It contains project management activities and key information regarding the project (agreements, deliverables, milestones, email lists, reporting, risk registry, timelines, project monitoring and control tables, instructions, etc.). It also facilitates governance, WP and task meetings, work plans, task lists, notes, etc. In addition, Google Drive is used for activities that cannot easily be done on Eduuni Wiki, i.e., for co-creating materials (text, presentations, tables) requiring multiple persons working simultaneously on the same file. Google Drive provides a platform for team members to store, share, and collaborate on files in real-time. The EOSC EDEN Google Drive folders are well-structured and will be updated periodically to meet the evolving needs of each WP throughout the project.

All public documents and data will be shared on Zenodo throughout and at the end of the project. Non-public documents (e.g., meeting minutes) and certain data (e.g., anonymized data) will be stored in the EOSC EDEN

¹² CARE principles <https://ardc.edu.au/resource/the-care-principles/>

¹³ Lin, D., Crabtree, J., Dillo, I., Downs, R. R., Edmunds, R., Giaretta, D., ... & Westbrook, J. (2020). The TRUST Principles for digital repositories. *Scientific data*, 7(1), 144.

¹⁴ EU Open Research Repository <https://zenodo.org/communities/eu/>

¹⁵ MARCXML. <https://www.loc.gov/standards/marcxml/>

¹⁶ Dublin Core™. <https://www.dublincore.org/specifications/dublin-core/>

¹⁷ DataCite Metadata Schema 4.6. <https://schema.datacite.org/meta/kernel-4.6/>

¹⁸ Eduuni-workspaces. <https://tt.eduuni.fi/SitePages/Home.aspx>

Wiki throughout the project and preserved for another 5 years after the project. The EOSC EDEN Wiki is managed by CSC.

2.2 Making data accessible

To promote reuse and broader application of project results, data is made available on open platforms unless the data owner provides a valid reason to restrict access. If a decision is made to keep data confidential, the reason will be documented in an updated version of the DMP.

All data, except for identified sensitive data, will be made public. Data (e.g., anonymised survey data and supporting documentation) will be deposited in the EOSC EDEN Zenodo community. At this stage of the project, there are no legal or contractual obligations for specific beneficiaries to keep their data confidential. The data will remain available and findable in the public repository. Metadata is required to be provided along with the data or project outputs, which will be publicly available under the funding agreement and licensed under the public domain. It contains rich information to enable users to access the data. Metadata and data files will be accessible through a free and standardized access protocol¹⁹ such as HTTP and OAI-PMH. For highly sensitive data, for which it is not possible to provide secure access through a fully mechanized protocol, a responsible person will be assigned an email and official phone number to discuss data access issues during and after the data access period.

At this stage of the project, no injunctions were imposed to allow time to publish or seek intellectual property protection (e.g., patents). If so, project partners would need to explain why the action was imposed and how long it would last and update this in the updated version of the DMP, bearing in mind that the data should be made available as soon as possible. Currently, EOSC EDEN does not have a formal Data Access Committee (e.g., to evaluate and approve access requests for personal or sensitive data). Instead, the project relies on the protocol established within the Plan for Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication.

2.3 Making data interoperable

EOSC EDEN will use data and metadata in common standard formats, follow community-agreed best practices for interoperability, and ensure that the data produced can be analysed together with other data types. As datasets are identified and collected, updates to (meta)data creation standards will be outlined in the following DMP releases. To describe data and metadata, vocabularies will be used that provide terms or concepts that adequately represent their content. These vocabularies will also adhere to FAIR guidelines.

Where possible, metadata follows the widely accepted Dublin Core and DataCite schema. Data will include qualified cross-references to other data if the generated dataset builds on a previously generated dataset, or if the previous dataset is necessary to complete the new data, or if complementary information is stored in a different dataset.

To improve interoperability and consistency of data, vocabulary control is encouraged to align key terms and definitions between WPs and with the sister project FIDELIS. Several relevant terminologies, such as CODATA Research Data Management Terminology²⁰ and UNESCO Open Science²¹, may be referenced.

¹⁹ Zenodo General Policies v1.0. <https://about.zenodo.org/policies/>

²⁰ CODATA Research Data Management Terminology. <https://vocabs.ardc.edu.au/viewById/685>

²¹ UNESCO Open Science. <https://www.unesco.org/en/open-science/open-science-glossary>

2.4 Increase data re-use

It is not expected that there will be any restrictions or licensing requirements on the sharing or reuse of the data by third parties. EOSC EDEN will strive to use solutions that are as open as possible and licenses suitable for data sharing. The project will make extensive use of PIDs (e.g., DOI for publication and ORCID for authors) and leverage reference metadata in providing discovery metadata, i.e., semantic artefacts. The data produced in the project will be usable by third parties, even after the end of the project.

3 Other outputs

All types of public project results, documents and data will be open for comment, stored in Zenodo, and published on the project web platform as soon as they are available. All outputs, except for certain confidential information (e.g., administrative items containing legal, financial, or sensitive information), will be deposited under a CC-BY 4.0 license, accompanied by sufficient metadata. With consent and a proper data-sharing agreement, certain data and results will be shared with closely collaborating projects, e.g., the FIDELIS project, while ensuring the protection of data confidentiality. Confidential/sensitive information will not be disclosed or used other than for the purpose for which it was collected. EOSC EDEN is committed to sharing its results publicly as early as possible.

4 Allocation of resources

Partners use primarily free trusted data repositories (e.g., EOSC EDEN Zenodo community) or domain-specific data repositories or other curated repositories such as national/institutional to which the organisations subscribe. Resources for data management are implemented in WP5, including co-working using the EOSC EDEN project Wiki and SharePoint, where the Eduuni Services are located at CSC's data centre in Finland. The main contact/principal investigator of each partner will be responsible for data management within the WP and in EOSC EDEN Zenodo, including updates and implementation according to the rules and deadlines set out in this DMP. A further evaluation and update of this DMP will be conducted at M36 and aligned with EOSC EDEN management and progress reporting.

5 Data security

Data should be collected following standard operating procedures in open, non-proprietary formats. If the data contains identifiable information, it is stored in a secure environment, with the stored data backed up frequently. The primary responsibility for data security lies with the data collection partner. Sensitive data (i.e. raw interview and survey data) collected as part of EOSC EDEN will be stored at the partner's institution securely, and the transcription of the interview can be security held and shared via CSC's SD Connect.

The EOSC EDEN Wiki space is visible and accessible only to the individuals who are working on the project, including finance and admin personnel. The project Wiki space is maintained on the CSC RDI Project Collaboration Wiki on Eduuni¹³, which is implemented with the Atlassian Confluence product. All Eduuni Services are located at CSC's data centre in Finland. Certain data (without sensitive information) will be archived in the EOSC EDEN Wiki with appropriate access and security controls. Data stored in the EOSC EDEN Wiki will be automatically backed up once a week.

EOSC EDEN Google Drive is accessible to all consortium members, including finance and admin personnel. Access rights to the EOSC EDEN shared drive are managed by CSC. Google stores data on off-site backup media to help ensure recovery from any catastrophic errors or natural disasters in one of its data centres.

For those project results (e.g., publications and presentations) published in Zenodo, each file will have two independent MD5 checksums. One of these checksums is stored by CERN's EOS service²², and used for automatic detection and recovery of file corruption on disks²³.

Regarding data sharing and security control with the FIDELIS project, regular joint PMB meetings will be conducted to discuss and address data-sharing matters between the two projects. These meetings will aim to establish a clear agreement on the scope of data transfer and the measures to ensure its security, particularly for data that may raise potential ethical concerns. Furthermore, the data-sharing plan will be explicitly outlined in the informed consent form, which will require consent from the participants/data subjects.

6 Ethics

During activities such as surveys, interviews and workshops with various external organizations or individuals, EOSC EDEN adheres to the ethical standards, values and data protection requirements outlined in the Grant Agreement. While each partner remains responsible for their actions, the project ensures a consistent and responsible approach to these considerations. Project ethics statements and informed consent templates will be discussed and drafted before conducting activities involving human participants and personal data. The EOSC EDEN privacy policy is published on the project website²⁴.

The EOSC EDEN partners function as joint data controllers under the EU GDPR. Through the EOSC EDEN website, contact and other personal data (email, sensitive information such as gender or dietary requirements required for organizing events) will be collected for project activities such as workshops and bootcamps, surveys, registrations for newsletters and mailing lists. The project only collects the personal data necessary to meet its information needs, adhering to the principle of data minimization. While collecting personal data, informed consent is required to ensure that participants fully understand the purpose of data collection, how the data will be used, with whom the data will be shared, and other necessary information (if possible). Project partners may process this data if required for the project if the processing is compliant with the GDPR. The joint website of EOSC EDEN and FIDELIS will also remain operational for 5 years after the end of the project.

The personal data of project partners collected to manage project activities will not be shared externally unless there is a legitimate reason. Such sharing will only be done with the agreement reached at the relevant project meeting and with the consent of the parties concerned.

7 Other issues

EOSC EDEN partners agree to the principles and good practices in the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity (ALLEA, 2023)²⁵. In addition, project partners may have their own national and/or institutional data management policies for the data they are responsible for. Most project partners are based in the EU, while the consortium also includes partners from Norway (UiT), Switzerland (CERN), and the United Kingdom (JESSEX-UKDA and Arkivum), and thus, activities will be conducted in those countries. However,

²² CERN's EOS service. <https://eos-web.web.cern.ch/eos-web/>

²³ Zenodo Infrastructure. <https://about.zenodo.org/infrastructure/>

²⁴ EOSC EDEN Privacy Policy. <https://eden-fidelis.eu/privacy-policy>

²⁵ The European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity REVISED EDITION 2023.

https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/horizon/guidance/european-code-of-conduct-for-research-integrity_horizon_en.pdf

none of the undertaken activities in these countries raise potential ethical issues. Also, import or export (other than data) from non-EU countries is not in the scope of the proposal.

EOSC EDEN will be supported by an External Advisory Board (EAB) consisting of six experts recognized at the European and global level in the fields covered by the project or representatives of the target stakeholder groups. The EAB will meet twice a year (one teleconference and one face-to-face meeting) to provide advisory support to EOSC EDEN. The EAB members will sign a non-disclosure agreement (NDA) as per the consortium agreement signed by the EOSC EDEN consortium in February 2025 to formally acknowledge that they may receive confidential information during their participation in the EAB and that they commit not to disclose it.

8 References

No	Description/Link
R1	EOSC EDEN. https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101188015
R2	The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. https://www.nature.com/articles/sdata201618
R3	Open Science. https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/strategy/strategy-research-and-innovation/our-digital-future/open-science_en
R4	GDPR. https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32016R0679
R5	INFRAEOSC. https://rea.ec.europa.eu/funding-and-grants/horizon-europe-research-infrastructures/enabling-operational-open-and-fair-eosc-ecosystem-infraeosc_en
R6	FIDELIS. https://eosc.eu/eu-project/fidelis/
R7	EOSC EDEN Zenodo community. https://zenodo.org/communities/eosceden/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest
R8	EOSC EDEN GitHub. https://github.com/EOSC-EDEN
R9	SD Connect. https://sd-connect.csc.fi/
R10	EOSC EDEN acknowledgement instruction. https://Wiki.eduuni.fi/x/alN9IQ .
R11	Free Software Licensing Resources. https://www.fsf.org/licensing/education/?set_language=da
R12	CARE Principles. https://ardc.edu.au/resource/the-care-principles/
R13	Lin, D., Crabtree, J., Dillo, I., Downs, R. R., Edmunds, R., Giaretta, D., ... & Westbrook, J. (2020). The TRUST Principles for digital repositories. <i>Scientific data</i> , 7(1), 144.
R14	EU Open Research Repository https://zenodo.org/communities/eu/
R15	MARCXML. https://www.loc.gov/standards/marcxml/
R16	Dublin Core™. https://www.dublincore.org/specifications/dublin-core/
R17	DataCite Metadata Schema 4.6. https://schema.datacite.org/meta/kernel-4.6/
R18	Eduuni-workspaces. https://tt.eduuni.fi/SitePages/Home.aspx
R19	Zenodo General Policies v1.0. https://about.zenodo.org/policies/
R20	CODATA Research Data Management Terminology. https://vocab.ardc.edu.au/viewById/685
R21	UNESCO Open Science. https://www.unesco.org/en/open-science/open-science-glossary
R22	CERN's EOS service. https://eos-web.web.cern.ch/eos-web/

R23	Zenodo Infrastructure. https://about.zenodo.org/infrastructure/
R24	The European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity REVISED EDITION 2023. https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/horizon/guidance/european-code-of-conduct-for-research-integrity_horizon_en.pdf